

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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Sato-Umi or Harmony with Nature

20th ICHA, Hiroshima 2023

Torii gate that welcomes visitors to the Itsukushima Shrine Island (Miyajima), UNESCO World Heritage at Hiroshima, Seto Inland Sea. Photo E. Bresnan

As the global outbreak of the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) had finally calmed down, the 20th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA 2023) was held in Hiroshima, Japan, bringing together more than 500 participants from 40 countries around the world for the first time in five years. The Local Organizing Committee (LOC), chaired by Prof Ichiro Imai and the Scientific Committee (SC) of ICHA 2023 would like

to express their gratitude to the ISSHA Council executives and participants for their various forms of cooperation.

During the preparation of ICHA 2023, the LOC has been facing difficulties derived from the COVID19 pandemic and rising prices in travelling costs. In this exceptional situation, we appreciate ISSHA members understanding about our giving up the original plan of an online and in person hybrid meeting

Local Organizing Committee for the 20th ICHA. From left to right: Satoshi Nagai (Vicechair), Kazuiko Koike (Vicechair), Masao Adachi (chair of program committee), Toshiyuki Suzuki (Vicechair), Ichiro Imai (Chair), Natsu Nakayama (secretariat) and Shigeru Itakura. Photo LOC ICHA 2023.

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Participants in the 20th ICHA, Hiroshima 2023. Photo LOC ICHA 2023.

that was initially announced by the LOC, and holding a conventional in-person meeting.

Japanese people have a long history of intimate ties with the coastal environment. This is defined by the “Sato-Umi” concept whereby biological productivity and biodiversity have been nourished through the intimate interactions of humans with their coastal ecosystems.

The theme of the 20th ICHA conference was “HAB Science and Human Well-being”. The goal was to exchange relevant scientific information towards a greater understanding of HAB mechanisms, better and timely predictions of HAB occurrences and mitigation of their negative impacts.

In addition to the Opening Lecture and 9 Plenary Lectures, there were 216

oral communications, 45 ignite talks and 199 posters on 16 different topics: Ecology; Biology and Biogeography; Community/Species Interactions; Taxonomy; Microbiomes and Omics; Prediction and Modelling; Monitoring and Mitigation; Ciguatera and Benthic-, Ichthyotoxic- and Cyanobacterial HABs; Toxins, Biosynthesis and detec-

tion methods; Toxicology; Surveillance and Management; HABs in a changing world; Socio-economic impacts and Emerging issues.

We are convinced that the ICHA 2023 has made a significant contribution to the scientific knowledge on harmful algae, and we sincerely hope that all participants thoroughly enjoyed their experiences in Hiroshima, the International City of Peace, along with Japanese cuisine and Sake.

Finally, we extend our deep appreciation to Dr. Wayne Litaker, our leaving ISSHA president, for the tremendous support provided over the past year to the preparation of ICHA 2023.

Prof. Ichiro Imai
Chair of the LOC of ICHA 2023

What conditions caused naughty algal blooms to turn into harmful ones?

Fukuyo-sensei opened the conference with a colourful review of red tide events and increasing fish cultivation in the Seto Inland Sea. "Microalgae are kinds of friends struggling in the sea, in the same way as I do on land. This way

of thinking may be quite specific for Japanese, or only me? In Japan we have various stone monuments for those we used to utilize as food or tools in order to express our gratitude and to pray for repose of souls of living things and spirits

staying in instruments. In Japanese way, I feel naughty microalgae are friends working together, although I do not think to establish their monuments" (Yasuwo Fukuyo, ICHA 2023, Hiroshima).

Long term series of red tides events and yellow-tail aquaculture; control measures applied in the late 70's. From Fukuyo-sensei ICHA 2023 opening address with his kind permission.

Aerial view of fish cages at the Seto Inland Sea (left) and the same area with a red tide aggregated around the cultures site. Images from the Seto Inland Sea Fisheries Agency taken from Fukuyo-sensei ICHA 2023 opening address with his kind permission.

two decades of monitoring and study using molecular tools: metabarcoding looks promising as an early warning tool and degradation of coral reefs may favour conditions for the proliferation of benthic harmful algal blooms (BHABs) caused by *Ostreopsis* and *Gambierdiscus* species. Concerning ciguatera poisoning (CP), **Masao Adachi** highlighted that different taxa could be the potential causative organisms of CP outbreaks in Japan: i) *Gambierdiscus silvae* that may produce Caribbean ciguatoxins (C-CTXs) or CTX-like toxins; ii) new undescribed *Gambierdiscus* phylogenotypes detected by metabarcoding analysis or iii) unknown organisms including genera other than *Gambierdiscus* may produce P-CTXs. **Luiz L. Mafra Jr** presented laboratory and field surveys indicating that plastic pollution might increasingly exacerbate the negative impacts of BHABs on marine organisms and human health through the food web in certain coastal areas.

Esther Garcés and **Mari Yotsu-Yamashita** addressed parasitic interactions and toxin pathways, respectively. **Esther** highlighted the conspicuous presence, in high-density mono-specific blooms of different dinoflagellate species, of numerous parasitoid species, some of them recurrently detected and sometimes coexisting in the same host species, and clearly some of them representing new diversity yet to be described. These parasitoids appear to have adapted to their hosts, thereby facilitating the maintenance, spread and recurrence of the parasite populations. **Mari** presented recent findings in the biosynthesis and metabolic pathways for tetrodotoxin and paralytic shellfish toxins using putative biosynthetic intermediates of saxitoxin (STX) and stable isotope-labelled compounds.

Oral presentations

There were 36 parallel oral sessions which included 216 presentations in 16 categories. Some highlights are summarised below.

1. Ecology

This topic covered ecological studies of a wide range of organisms: cyanobacteria, haptophytes, diatoms, dinoflagellates and their related grazers, parasites and viruses. In these studies, data were collected using different methods, including morpholo-

Fukuyo-sensei (centre) and WESTPAC colleagues. Photo CP Leaw.

gy-based automatic imaging instruments [e.g., Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB)], molecular tools [e.g., metabarcoding and quantitative PCR (qPCR)], chemotaxonomy (based on pigment analysis by HPLC), multi-omics approaches, or a combination of them.

Molecular tools are increasingly applied to monitor HAB species. Examples included metabarcoding alone in Japan (**Sirje Sildever**) or in combination with other methods for cyanobacteria in the USA (**Christopher J. Gobler**); and a new single-cell multiplex PCR assay developed to assess the genotype frequency and toxin dynamics of *Pyrodinium bahamense* (**Kathleen Cusick**). Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) used to identify the mechanisms driving the development and decline of *Dinophysis acuminata* blooms in the Nauset Marsh (USA) imaged *in situ* for the first time thin layer dynamics and phased mating processes in this species (**Serena Sung-Clarke**) and protozooplanktonic grazers later used in laboratory estimates of grazing losses (**Megan Ladds**).

Analysis of long-term data series supported the development of a conceptual model illustrating atmosphere-ocean interactions in the Magellan fjords region (Chile); the unprecedented retreat of ice fields is impacting the fjords circulation dynamics and the subsequent changes in plankton community structure, including HAB events (**Máximo Frangopulos**).

An 18-years-record of toxic dinoflagellate cysts in NW Africa, obtained with sediment traps was related to atmospheric and hydrographic changes to identify the drivers of cyst production and explore future trends (**Surya Eldo Virma Roza**).

Some emerging issues included the description of a great diversity of HAB species and abundance of *Alexandrium* cells found on drifting plastics in the Philippines (**Deo Florence L. Onda**) and new findings on the biological interactions between the high biomass bloom forming *Lepidodinium chlorophorum*, potentially harmful to oysters, and bacteria. The dinoflagellate production of Transparent Exopolymer Particles (TEPs) may facilitate positive bacterial interactions and nutrients availability (**Raffaele Siano**).

Last but not least, 'Objectif Plancton', a citizen science program to assess phytoplankton communities' changes in France, was presented (**Laura Schweibold**).

2. Biology and Biogeography

Extraordinary progress was presented concerning genetic trends that can help to explain evolutionary processes as well as the current ecological niches and biogeographic distributions of some HAB species.

For instance, transcriptomes of 17 dinoflagellate strains and phylogenetic analyses based on large multi-gene alignments of proteins and nucleotides

indicated that the *sxtA* gene may not have been laterally transferred between *Alexandrium* species and the related genus *Centrodinium punctatum* (**Shauna A. Murray**). Laboratory culture-based observations demonstrated sexual mating, formation of planozygotes and diploid cysts, and cyst germination in *Karenia mikimotoi*, *Karlodinium veneticum*, *Prorocentrum donghaiense* and *Akashiwo sanguinea*. The presence of resting cysts of these species was confirmed and their distribution in sediments from Chinese seas determined using a combination of fluorescence in situ hybridization; light microscopy; single cyst sequencing for an ~1400 bp LSU rRNA gene (FISH-LM-SCS) and qPCR (**Ying Zhong Tang**). A comprehensive genomic study revealed that the mitochondrial genes are relatively unstable compared to plastidial genes in nine *Skeletonema* species (**Satoshi Nagai**). Results from laboratory experiments on the response of *K. mikimotoi* to light intensity (Fv/Fm curves) suggested that migration of field population from surface to sub-surface layers was to avoid inhibition of their PSII and get the optimal light irradiance (**Shota Higo**).

3. Community/Species Interactions

Very interesting studies were presented on this topic combining cutting-edge experimental and analytical methods. This is an area that will certainly offer new progress in the near future to our understanding of small scale biological interactions involved in the development of HABs.

As an example, transcriptome and proteome analysis revealed that grazing by the protist *Paramecium* induced changes in multiple life cycle and metabolic processes in the cyanobacteria *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* including heterocyst differentiation and enhancement of nitrogen fixation (**Yuan Huang**). Different laboratory experiments explored the allelochemical compounds and mechanisms of action among different microalgae. Free Fatty Acids (FFA) and Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) can affect *Gymnodinium catenatum* (**Martin Fernando Encinas-Yanez**), while the mucilage produced by benthic microalgae contributes to transport of allelochemical compounds (**Nadia V. Herrera-Herrera**). Interestingly, seaweed cultivation could en-

hance the biodiversity of the co-occurring planktonic community (**Zhaoyang Chai**).

4. Taxonomy

This topic included new progress on the taxonomy of several harmful taxa in coastal areas. The studies combined light microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and molecular sequencing applied to field samples and isolates of *Amphidoma*, *Coolia*, *Heterocapsa*, *Karenia*, *Karlodinium*, *Noctiluca*, *Protocera-tium*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Pyrodinium bahamense*, certain raphidophytes, nanoflagellates and cyanobacteria.

Information on new descriptions in taxonomy, combined with the toxicological characterization of the species is regularly updated in the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae, (**Nina Lundholm**) and drives the re-evaluation of certain groups of toxins, such as the goniodomins produced by some *Alexandrium* species (**Urban Tillmann**). On the evolutionary side, a study on plastid molecular phylogeny suggested that the Kareniaceae started from an ancestral species with transient haptophyte symbionts; subsequently, 13 derivative lineages independently established the permanent plastids (**Kazuya Takahashi**).

5. Microbiomes and Omics

This topic focused on several cutting-edge molecular approaches (e.g., metabarcoding, metagenome analysis, metatranscriptomics and metabolomics) used to investigate microbiome diversity or relationships within the microbial communities. Four communications addressing different microalgal groups were highlighted.

The combination of traditional culture-based methods with high throughput 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing was applied to analyse the microbiome composition associated with four *Gambierdiscus* species (*G. carpenteri*, *G. lewisii*, *G. lapillus* and a second *G. lapillus*-related genotype (**Shikder Saiful Islam**). The study revealed a high diversity and species-specific bacterial composition with relevant biogeochemical and functional roles affecting growth dynamics of these dinoflagellates. A full-length 18S rDNA metabarcoding analysis of samples from the Texas Observatory for Algal Succession Time (TOAST) re-

vealed that HABs diversity increased after an extreme event (**Lisa Campbell**).

Metatranscriptomics and metabolomics aligned with ecological metadata revealed that the ichthyotoxic mixotroph *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* exploits its toxicity to dominate the community and increase its prey availability for nutritional supplementation (**Uwe John**). The success of the spreading and massive bloom formation of the microbenthic diatom *Cymbella janischii* may be favoured by bacteria in the mucous mat able to synthesize B-vitamins and with genes encoding the hydrolysis of diphosphates. Furthermore, a 3D reconstruction of the mats using microscopy and nano-focus X-ray CT supports the idea that the interior of the mat is filled with a dense soup of organic substances, which could be utilized by co-existing organisms (**Shinya Soto**).

6. Prediction and Modeling

Several communications presented modelling or machine and deep learning approaches aimed to predict HAB events and manage their effects.

Trophic-transfer models throughout a critical marine food chain are constructed to predict the exposure to STXs of walrus in the Alaskan Arctic (**Patrick Charapata**).

In the Philippines, the feasibility of establishing an automated HAB monitoring pipeline utilizing IFCB is investigated by training and evaluating a series of tree-based and convolutional neural network models in the identification and quantification of local HAB species (**Paul Samuel Ignacio**). In Malaysia, machine learning models are developed to predict the occurrence of *Pyrodinium bahamense* and *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* (**Teruaki Yoshida**). Microalgal abundance measurements from the Sabah's Department of Fisheries are combined with oceanic data (sea surface temperature and salinity, wind velocity, solar irradiance and chlorophyll a) provided by Copernicus Marine Services and NASA POWER databases. In Alfacos Bay (Spain, Western Mediterranean), forecast models based on neural networks and built on phytoplankton times series, showed that five years of observations of *Karlodinium* provided optimal results, but a longer series was needed for *Pseudo-nitzschia* (**Margarita Fernández-Tejedor**). Abrupt changes in trends may diminish forecast capabilities

Left: The Sato-umi concept for HABs control applies the preservation of macroalgae and aquatic plants (*Zostera marina*) meadows as a basic strategy to prevent harmful proliferations exceeding alert levels. Right: If they exceed this threshold, the first prevention and mitigation strategy is to rake the sediments so that diatoms resting forms are resuspended and germinate, and their blooms outcompete noxious flagellates (e.g. *Chattonella*). Source: Imai et al [2]

and therefore a continuous improvement of the models is needed.

7. Monitoring and Mitigation

Many studies were presented exploring the opportunities and required research concerning a variety of methods aimed at monitoring HABs and mitigating their impacts.

A meta-analysis was conducted on the published and unpublished studies that used one of 28 chemical, bacterial, physical and/or plant-based algal bloom treatments in field experiments on various water quality measurements, including phytoplankton pigments and cell density, microcystin and off-flavours (Alan Wilson). The analysis concluded that most treatments failed to improve water quality in the field and highlighted the need for more research on alternative treatments. Similarly, experiments showed that hydrogen peroxide was not fully successful to control proliferations of the fish-killing *Prymnesium parvum* (Iwona Jasser). DinoSHIELD is a bio-control technology using alginate hydrogel to immobilize *Shewanella* sp. IRI-160. DinoSHIELDS continuously release bacteria-derived algicides targeting dinoflagellates while limiting the dispersion of bacteria. Promising results were obtained in the application of DinoSHIELDS tested in mesocosms studies in the Broadkill River, USA (Yanfei Wang) and in laboratory experiments with *Karenia brevis* (Kathryn J. Coyne). Detailed studies were presented characterizing the bio-flocculation agent obtained from the fruits of terrestrial plants, in particular

from *Diospyros mespiliformis*, which can be used to efficiently remove and lyse cyanobacterial cells (Jabunali R. Gumbo).

Exciting new nanopore field technology will soon be ready for commercialization (Robert George Hatfield). The assay presented uses recombinase polymerase amplification, an isothermal amplification technology that avoids some of the drawbacks of common PCR methods. Chilean HAB monitoring spans many scales and has recently incorporated metabarcoding and metagenomics technology to increase knowledge of the physiology and metabolism of phytoplankton communities and local HAB blooms (Gonzalo Fuenzalida). PhytO-ARM is a new and exciting open-source design toolkit to aid in the deployment and edge computing for IFCBs and other imagers on fixed and Lagrangian platforms (Michael Brosnahan). Concerning toxins, experiments to investigate the accumulation of dissolved domoic acid in mussels showed that these bivalves are not an adequate sentinel for that toxin, and alternate monitoring methods such as SPATT (solid phase adsorption toxin tracking) are more advantageous for understanding toxin concentration in the absence of harmful algal bloom (Aubrey Trapp).

8. Ciguatera and Benthic HABs

This topic covered chemistry, data science, ecology and physiology of BHABs such as *Gambierdiscus* and *Ostreopsis*. Particularly, bioactive compound screening and discovery, modelling and

biosensor development were advanced and noteworthy points.

The production of newly identified maitotoxins (MTXs, MTX-6 and -7) and gambierone analogues by two *Gambierdiscus* species, *G. cheloniae* and *G. honu*, were reported (J. Sam Murray). Production of C-CTX-5 from *G. silvae* was documented and the detailed stereochemical diversity of C-CTX analogues was discussed (Elizabeth M. Mudge). Experiments with a *G. polynesiensis* strain revealed the effects of temperature and salinity on growth and CTX production (Tomohiro Nishimura); modelling using these data sets predicted potential hotspots of this species' distribution and related ciguatera poisoning outbreaks in the future (Dana K. Briscoe). A promising biosensor for the detection of P-CTXs in fish and seawater (detection limit 10-fold lower than FDA guidance level) was developed (Mònica Campàs). A long term (2007–2021) study revealed *Ostreopsis* bloom trends along the Adriatic coast: densities increased until 2012 and declined from 2013 to date (Stefano Accoroni).

9. Ichthyotoxic HABs

The GlobalHAB “white paper” on fish-killing algae, recently published by IOC/UNESCO [3] was presented (Gustaaf M. Hallegraeff). This was the result of a workshop conducted in Puerto Varas, Chile, in October 2019, under the sponsorship of IOC, SCOR and the Government of Chile. It summarises current knowledge and gaps for future research about taxonomy, toxicity, bloom dynamics and impacts of fish-killing algal blooms. It provides

FISH-KILLING MARINE ALGAL BLOOMS: Causative Organisms, Ichthyotoxic Mechanisms, Impacts and Mitigation

G.M. Hallegraeff, D.M. Anderson, K. Davidson, F. Gianella, P.J. Hansen, H. Hegaret, M. Iwataki, T.O. Larsen, J. Mardones, L. Mackenzie, J.E. Rensel
Contributors: A.D. Cembella, O. Espinoza, L. Guzman, B. Krock, P.T. Lim, A.R. Place

a roadmap for scientists, aquaculturists and insurance brokers to improve the management of these events. A comprehensive study of the massive and unprecedented bloom of the ichthyotoxic haptophyte *Prymnesium parvum* in the River Oder in Poland/Germany was presented (**Elisabeth Varga**). Multiple drivers were identified and a combined effect of prymnesins and organic micro-pollutants was noticed. Another study revealed that *Karenia mikimotoi* significantly increased its ichthyotoxicity under axenic conditions, while different bacterial isolates could have different specific modulating effects on the algal ichthyotoxicity (**Fred Wang-Fat Lee**).

10. Cyanobacterial HABs

This topic covered chemistry, genomics, mitigation, monitoring by IFCB or molecular approaches including metabarcoding, and taxonomy of cyanobacteria from freshwater to marine benthic environments, with the following highlights.

The first toxic *Microcystis* blooms and several new genera were reported from Malaysia (**Yin Sing Ong**). A new toxic cyanobacterial genus and species, *Sphaerotherix gracilis*, with potential for industrial applications was reported from microplastic particles. (**Emily Curren**). New imaging and pulse shape cytometry techniques provided more precise and species-specific information on filamentous cyanobacteria (**Kaisa Kraft**). A novel early warning system using cyanotoxin-encoding genes predicted cyanotoxin production more accurately (**Jingrang Lu**). A new ELISA test detected most of the microcystin vari-

ants (**Ingunn A. Samdal**). Metabarcoding and LC-MS/MS analyses revealed benthic cyanobacterial mat diversity and their toxin production on Florida coasts (**David Erwin Berthold**). Potential recycling of food waste and cyanobacteria biomass by salt-tolerant mushroom strains was reported (**S. K. Sim**).

11. Toxins, Biosynthesis and Detection Methods

During the ICHA2023, we found out how the most novel methods are used to progress in the comprehension of toxin biosynthetic and metabolic pathways as well as in their detection. Thus, based on the colchicine mode of action, experiments suggest that STXs are biosynthesized *de novo* and also through salvage pathways (i.e. from intermediates in the degradative pathway). Colchicine inhibited nitrate assimilation upstream of glutamate biosynthesis in the *de novo* pathway (**Yuko Cho**). Using LC-HRMS analysis and culturing techniques, several uncommon okadaic acid and pectenotoxin analogues were found in *Dinophysis norvegica* from northeastern US coasts (**Christopher O. Miles**). A combination of short- and long-read amplicon sequencing, metatranscriptomics and metabolomics were used, with encouraging results, to characterize the oceanographic conditions associated with species-specific expression of domoic acid biosynthesis genes, in connection with elevated particulate domoic acid concentrations in Santa Barbara Channel, USA in 2019–2022 (**Steffaney M. Wood**). Combining LC-MS/HRMS and LC-MS/MS, novel toxins, cyclic amines and products of their metabolism from *Vulcanodinium rugosum* were identified and quantified in contaminated shellfish in the Ingril lagoon hotspot in France (**Vincent Hort**). HPLC coupled with ion-mobility QTOF mass spectrometry, showed that the structural diversity of the prymnesins produced by *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* was larger than previously reported. Additional bioassays using RT-gill-W1 gill cells are run to identify the ichthyotoxins produced by this fish-killing microalga (**Thomas O. Larsen**).

12. Toxicology

An in-depth revision is required on the toxicity of toxin groups, toxicity equivalency factors, and how all this is being

conditioned by the accelerating change in the toxin profiles worldwide (but especially in Europe) due to global warming. Regulatory limits and toxicological endpoints for many toxin groups, including CTX, OA and STX, were analysed (**Luis M. Botana**).

Microalgal toxins are part of still poorly understood chemical ecology. The effect of dinophysistoxin-1 (DTX-1) was studied on the growth, photosynthesis, antioxidant responses and cell cycle of the haptophyte *Isochrysis galbana*. DTX-1 was found to provoke cell cycle arrest in the G2/M phase, and the cell size and intracellular complexity were also increased in the 24-h batch culture (**Jiangbing Qiu**).

13. Surveillance and Management

This topic covered chemistry, developing monitoring tools using molecular approaches including high-throughput microfluidic real-time qPCR technology, and developing monitoring frameworks, with the following highlights.

An effective analysis method using a high-throughput PCR system, Biomark HD real-time qPCR System, for the six *Alexandrium* species was reported (**Francesca Cucchi**). From researchers to volunteers, from qPCR to drones and satellites including the unintentional dogs, exciting and effective approaches to HAB monitoring in the USA were presented (**Hannah Bonner**). A duplex PCR assay targeting STX synthesis genes, *sxtA4* and *sxtG* genes, was described as a promising tool for the early monitoring strategies of STX in aquaculture sites (**Greta Gaiani**). *Alexandrium catenella* blooms may originate in Los Lagos region, Chile, and be dispersed to other aquaculture areas by hydrodynamics (**Óscar Espinoza-González**).

14. HABs in a Changing World

This topic reported a wide range of studies to investigate bloom mechanisms of HABs influenced by climate change. The studies investigated HABs by various methods of chemistry, data science (modelling or statistical analysis), dynamics, ecology including mixotrophy, palynology combined with eDNA analysis, and physiology (growth experiments coupled with toxin production and molecular changes). Focused organisms were mainly dinoflagellates (*Alexandrium*, *Gambierdiscus*, *Karenia* and *Ostreopsis*), diatom

(*Pseudo-nitzschia*) and microcystin-producing cyanobacteria.

There is new evidence of unexpected variability due to climate change which hinders prediction of when and where HAB events will occur in a future ocean. These uncertainties affected studies on *Karenia brevis* and benthic microalgal species such as *Gambierdiscus* in the Gulf of Mexico (**Patricia M. Glibert, Sabrina Heiser**), *Karenia selliformis* in Hokkaido, Japan (**Tomonori Isada**), HAB species in the Bohai Sea and Yellow Sea, China (**Rencheng Yu**), *Gambierdiscus* and *Ostreopsis* on Jeju coasts, Korea (**Wonho Yih**), and *Alexandrium minutum* in the northwestern Iberian Peninsula, Spain (**Francisco Rodríguez**). Conceptual models were raised: for the toxic *Alexandrium catenella* blooms in the Alaskan Arctic (**Donald M. Anderson**) and for predicting future changes in *Alexandrium* bloom dynamics and toxicity of shellfish in Southeast Alaska (**John R. Harley**). Warmer conditions may increase dissolved DA production by *Pseudo-nitzschia multiseriata* (**Raphael M. Kudela**) while rising pCO₂ does not affect either its growth or toxin production (**William P. Cochlan**). A nature-based solution was established to eliminate cyanotoxins in freshwater using biologically enhanced biocarbon (biochar) (**Jane Moore**).

15. Socio-economic Impacts

Revealing the socio-economic impacts can influence policy formulations to establish better HAB monitoring strategies (**Mark Leonard S. Silaras**). The studies in this category, therefore, investigated and summarised the current status and ongoing projects on social and economic impacts of HABs. The analysis of newspapers published in Japan between 1872 and 2023 revealed a social 'alarmist' perception of HABs and shellfish poisonings (**Kazumi Wakita**). Natural sciences cannot be isolated from society: in the Philippines, HABs cause major economic losses to small-scale fishing communities (**Mark Leonard S. Silaras, Leni G. Yap-Dejeto**).

16. Emerging Issues

This topic was mainly focused on toxin bioaccumulation and related physiological mechanisms in shellfish. In addition, symptoms of severe acute dermatitis caused by toxins were reported. Investigation into the adsorption of toxins on virgin

and aged microplastics and an international qPCR workshop promoted by GlobalHAB were also reported.

Significant progress in understanding the action mechanisms of some toxins was reported: microcystin inhaled in mice (**Jiyoung Lee**) and portimine A causing dermatitis in fishermen associated with a bloom of *Vulcanodinium rugosum* in Senegal (**Philipp Hess**). New insights into cellular processes underlying the slow depuration of DA in King scallops were reported (**José Luis García-Corona**).

Ignite talks

There were two poster sessions including 244 presentations in 16 categories. Highlights of three Ignite Talk sessions covering 45 presentations, follow.

A large-scale *Alexandrium catenella* bloom was first detected in the northern Bering Sea using an IFCB (**Evangelina Fachon**). New Phagomyxa-like parasitoids were detected and isolated from Korean coastal waters (**Ye Seul Jeong**). Accumulation of CTXs in herbivorous fish from Okinawa was confirmed and their dietary preferences elucidated using metabarcoding analysis (**Goshi Araki**). Progress in the understanding of the biosynthesis of 5-hydroxymethyl uracil, the unique nucleotide replacing about forty percent of thymidine in dinoflagellates, may provide some keys to design specific strategies for HAB mitigation (**Emily Jolly**). Various topics from freshwater lakes to tropical oceans with specific focus on viruses, bacteria, silicate skeletons and even plastic waste were reported (**Juri Nazareth Mapa Ochotorena, Masaki Fujita, Kazumasa Yamada, Denise Ching Yi Yu**). Two mitigation techniques used carbon nanostructures to remove HAB toxins and modified clay spreading to remove HAB species (**Amparo Alfonso, Jennifer H. Toyoda**). Other topics included detection perspectives, new red tides, environmental quality control, parasites, ichthyotoxins, life cycles, effect of toxins on marine organisms and on model organisms, environmental cycles, and shellfish toxin profiles..

Acknowledgements

It would have been impossible to write up this highlight article without the help of the oral speakers and session chairs who summarised the highlight information to us. We greatly appre-

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References

1. Van de Waal D & Garcés E 2022. In: Reguera B & Bresnan E (eds) HAN 69: pp 4–9 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6136273>
2. Imai, I et al 2021. Fish Sci 87:437–464
3. GlobalHAB 2023. IOC Manuals and Guides 93 <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000387393>

Authors

Tomohiro Nishimura, Fisheries Technology Institute, Japan Fisheries Research and Education Agency (FRA), 2-17-5 Maruishi, Hatsukaichi, Hiroshima 739-0452, Japan

Elisa Berdalet, Institute of Marine Sciences (ICM-CSIC), Passeig Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37-49, Barcelona 08003, Spain

Email corresponding authors (these authors contributed equally to this work): nishimura_tomohiro49@fra.go.jp berdalet@icm.csic.es

The authors, Elisa Berdalet (left) and Tomohiro Nishimura (right). Photo at the Gala Dinner, ICHA2023.

ISSHA Societal Activities during the 20th ICHA Conference

The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) convened the 20th International Conference on Harmful Algae, held in Hiroshima, Japan, from 5-10 November 2023. The ISSHA Council had various meetings between May and November 2023 to organize the Conference activities, Council elections, travel awards, achievement awards and the ISSHA General Assembly.

General Assembly

The ISSHA General Assembly was held on Monday 6 November from 19:00 to 20:30. The General Assembly was opened by President Wayne Litaker and minutes from the previous assembly were approved. Various updates were provided including proposed by-law changes (Ian Jenkinson; see below), achievement awards (Dedmer van de Waal; see below), update on the Young Investigator Network Meeting (Misty

Peacock, see below), ISSHA Treasurer's report (Nina Lundholm), Travel Awards (Po Teen Lim; see below), updates about the ICHA 2023 proceedings (Esther Garces and Ichiro Imai), details regarding ICHA2023 (Ichiro Imai), Council election results (Wayne Litaker; see below), and presentation of the ICHA 2027 in Aberdeen, Scotland (Christine Edwards). The General Assembly was followed by a presentation of the ICHA 2025 that will be held in Punta Arenas, Chile (Leanardo Guzman).

By-law changes

The by-law changes that were proposed and approved included the addition of one or two student representatives to the ISSHA Council, the inclusion of a new clause in the ISSHA statutes with a 'code of conduct' to guard against harassment and discrimination, and the agreement that the approval of minutes from the General Assembly should be done within two months.

Young Investigators Network Meeting

This networking event was organized on Sunday 5 November by Misty Peacock, Natsuko Nakayama and Tomohiro Nishimura. It consisted of different ac-

tivities, including games to illustrate effective communication, and listening, and participants discussed how to present oneself confidently. A total of 19 early career scientists attended the event.

Travel Awards

Travel awards have been given to a total of 36 young researchers and members of the International Society for the study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) to participate the International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA2023) in Hiroshima city, Japan, from 5-10 November 2023. This biennial event is the biggest event for harmful algae researchers. The call for travel award application was announced through the website of ISSHA six months before the event, and applicants submitted their applications through the link of a google form available on the website. The call was also disseminated through emails to reach out to wider audiences of the HAB research community. All applications were evaluated by the ISSHA Travel Award Committee. With the funding from the Scientific Committee on Ocean Research (SCOR), five young scientists from the developing countries (China, Malaysia, Chile, and Thailand) were

Left: Frenzied activity at the ISSHA auction. Right: ISSHA Executive members and the new ISSHA President (right end) dressed for the occasion. Photos LOC ICHA 2023.

selected. ISSHA also provided ten additional travel awards with the funding from the society; this has benefited members from Australia, Austria, China, Ireland, Italy, New Zealand and United Kingdom. The funding support was obtained with the effort from the society to raise funds through the auction event held during each conference. We should not forget the generous support from all ISSHA members by donating items for the auction. In addition, nineteen postgraduate students and three HAB managers from the United States institutions were supported by the funding from NOAA, USA to attend the event in Hiroshima this year.

ISSHA Council members

ISSHA members voted on-line for the Executive Council, Council members and student representative. Some Council members stepped down after having (actively) served on previous Councils, including Vera Trainer (Past-president), Nina Lundholm (Treasurer), Elin Lindehoff (Secretary), Christine Band-Schmidt (chair of LOC ICHA 2021), Rosa Figueroa, Aifeng Li, Satoshi Nagai. Wayne Litaker thanked all past Council members for their services to ISSHA. Special thanks were made to Nina Lundholm for her long-standing service to the ISSHA Council, particularly as Treasurer.

The new ISSHA Executive and Council for the 2023-2025 period (new members and old ones occupying new executive positions are in italics):

Executive Council

- PRESIDENT: *Dedmer van de Waal* (The Netherlands)
- 1ST VICE PRESIDENT: *Po Teen Lim* (Malaysia)
- 2ND VICE PRESIDENT: *Lorena María Durán Riveroll* (Mexico)
- SECRETARY: *Ingrid Sassenhagen* (Germany)
- TREASURER: *Marie-Yasmine Dechraoui Bottein* (France)
- PAST-PRESIDENT: *Wayne Litaker* (United States)

Council members

- Leila Basti* (United Arab Emirates)
- Laura Biessy* (New Zealand)
- Christine Edwards* (United Kingdom)
- Henrik Enevoldsen* (Denmark)

- Esther Garcés* (Spain)
- Tim Harwood* (New Zealand)
- Philipp Hess* (France)
- Ichiro Imai* (Japan)
- Mitsunori Iwataki* (Japan)
- Ian Jenkinson* (France)
- Luiz Mafra, Jr.* (Brazil)
- Shauna Murray* (Australia)
- Antonella Penna* (Italy)
- Mary Carmen Ruiz De La Torre* (Mexico)
- Toshiyuki Suzuki* (Japan)

STUDENT REPRESENTATIVE:
Carolin Peter (Sweden)

The profiles of the ISSHA Council members can be found on the ISSHA website at [ISSHA Council](https://www.issha-council.org/).

ISSHA 2023 Achievement Awards

The ISSHA 2023 Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award was won by **Ichiro Imai** and **Mireille Chinain** for their groundbreaking work on harmful algae, their contribution to the research field, as well as to society, and their mentorship for many students. We were honored this year by our special guest Prof. Yasumoto, who personally handed over the awards to this year's winners, and Dr. Takayama, who made the wood carvings.

The nomination of **Ichiro Imai** was led by Satoshi Nagai and presented during the award ceremony by Donald Anderson. It was supported by 18 colleagues from around the world, in-

Carvings of Dr Takayama ready for the awardees. Photo LOC ICHA 2023.

cluding Japan (7), Malaysia (2), United States (3), Chile (2), Mexico (2), Germany, Estonia.

Ichiro Imai illuminated the overwintering process of *Chattonella* through his discovery of resting cysts in the bottom sediments of the Seto Inland Sea, Japan and succeeded in artificially producing and germinating cysts under laboratory culture conditions after years of difficult and sustained effort. He identified encystment and excystment mechanisms and elucidated the life cycle of *Chattonella* from the analysis of the nuclear phase with Dr. Mineo Yamaguchi using cultured strains. From the ecophysiological properties of cysts, Professor Imai has shown that monitoring bottom water temperatures in early summer is effective in predicting the cyst-driven initiation of red tide outbreaks. Prof. Imai also discovered the resting cysts of the raphidophyte *Heterosigma akashiwo*, a very important HB species that occurs in temperate waters worldwide, and once again, elucidated the mechanisms of bloom development, including overwintering and bloom initiation.

Prof. Imai expanded his studies to the distribution and ecophysiology of diatom resting stage cells, documented their abundance in the surface sediments, provided spatial maps of their distribution in Japanese coastal waters, and confirmed the importance of light for germination. These results are also a significant breakthrough in the study of community variation and population dynamics of microalgae. Prof. Imai furthermore demonstrated that diatoms can be induced to germination/revivification and rapid growth by resuspension to the euphotic layer using sediment perturbation. Application of these results has led to successful control of toxic blooms of *Alexandrium catenella* (formerly *A. tamarense*) in Osaka Bay (1400 km²), where bottom sediment perturbations over 5 km² were carried out by the Osaka Prefectural and Fisheries Cooperatives in the springs of 2020 to 2023.

Prof. Imai identified and isolated a large number of growth-inhibiting/algicidal bacteria from the Seto Inland Sea, such as *Cytophaga* and *Alteromonas*. He examined the effects of various algicidal bacteria on the growth of HAB species in co-culture experiments and revealed

Prof. Ichiro Imai with Donald M. Anderson (left) after receiving the Yasumoto Award. Photo credit: Don Anderson.

the dynamics of those interactions. In the field, he found that algicidal bacteria increased during the final stage of red tides, such as with *H. akashiwo* in Hiroshima Bay, Japan. Furthermore, in lakes and ponds, Prof. Imai discovered that cyanobactericidal bacteria and growth-inhibiting bacteria exist on the surface of aquatic plants with high densities. Based on these findings, practical measures to control nuisance cyanobacterial blooms were provided to secure safe water resources by artificially creating aquatic plant zones. The research on algicidal bacteria in the control of HABs has opened up a new research field in aquatic ecology, and research in this area is currently growing.

Prof. Imai contributed significantly to the instruction of many young scientists working in the field of aquatic ecology. For over a decade, he has been involved in reviewing applications for funding within the US HAB research program "The Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (ECO-HAB)." He has also contributed significantly to developing research societies such as the Plankton Society of Japan, the Japanese Society of Fisheries Science, and the Japanese Society of Microbial Ecology by being frequently invited or by helping to organize national and international conferences, symposia, and workshops. Of particular note is the honor of giving an invited lecture in June 2011 at the "Mycotoxins and Phycotoxins" session at the Gordon Research Conference in the United States, famous for its cutting-edge research presentations.

The nomination of **Mireille Chinain** was led by Patricia Tester and pre-

sented during the award ceremony by Marie-Yasmine Bottein. It was supported by nine colleagues from around the world, including China, French Polynesia (2), Australia, New Zealand, Mexico, and France (3). The following achievements were highlighted in the nomination letter, with the note that this is first time an ISSHA Yasumoto Award goes to a tropical Pacific scientist who is working at ground zero in ciguatera poisoning:

Mireille Chinain has played an integral part in all major breakthroughs in ciguatera research, such as chemical characterisation of ciguatoxin (with Dr. A. Legrand and Prof. T. Yasumoto), the taxonomic description of multiple *Gambierdiscus* species first based on morphology (with Dr. Faust) and later with help of genetics (with Dr. W. Litaker), the consistent production of ciguatoxin in culture by *G. polynesiensis*, the discovery of the new phenomenon of ciguatera poisoning from the gastropod *Tectus niloticus*, instigation in French Polynesia of an epidemiological surveillance program of human poisoning cases (with Dr. C. Gatti), and most importantly driving the elevation of ciguatera research as a priority topic for international forums such as IOC-IPHAB, FAO-WHO, and IAEA.

Since 2013, she has worked as an expert with the National Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health Safety (ANSES), in the "Ciguatoxins" working group, and since 2014 as an expert with the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). Since 2015 she served as one of the drivers for the Task Team on Global Inter-Agency Ciguatera Strategy for Improved Research and Management of IOC-UNESCO aimed at standardizing and strengthening research on ciguatera. Further Dr. Chinain has helped manage Ciguatera Poisoning (CP) risks at the international level serving as member of the FAO-WHO expert's meeting on CP in November 2018. She and her team hosted the IAEA Workshop on CP Field Monitoring and the Second Coordination Meeting of RAS 7/026 project in 2015. Being a highly valued and reliable collaborator, she has reached out over the years to many other others, e.g. in the US (Drs. M. Faust and W. Litaker), in Australia (Drs. R. Lewis, M. Holmes, S. Murry), the Pacific Island countries, China, and

Mireille Chinain, introduced by Marie Yasmine Dechraoui Bottein (right), accepts the Lifetime Achievement Award, bearing the name of Prof Yasumoto (left), in his esteemed presence. Photo credit: Clmence Gatti

mainland France, e.g., Dr. P. Hess to underpin the chemical understanding of the distribution of ciguatoxin analogues across tropical reef ecosystems. Materials Transfer Agreements were signed between ILM and the Cawthron Institute (Drs. P. Holland and L. Rhodes) New Zealand and NOAA (Dr. P. Tester) in the US as well. Mireille and her staff travelled from French Polynesia to Nantes to help support France's efforts to host ICHA2018.

The CIGUAPROD initiative coordinated and championed by Dr. Chinain, completed in 2019, aimed to generate a stand-alone facility for *Gambierdiscus* mass culture and toxin purification to provide her program, colleagues and eventually the HAB community with a reliable source of purified CTX standards. Even with the responsibilities of a laboratory, staff and innovative research and monitoring program, Dr Chinain has mentored numerous doctoral candidates working on various aspects of ciguatera.

Dr. Chinain's work has been acknowledged by national and international awards including the Prix Trgouboff Award 2005 in Marine Biology (Academy of Sciences of Paris, France), the Albert Szary Award 2006 (National Academy of Medicine, Paris, France), and Tyge Christensen Prize 2010 (International Phycological Society).

There are few, if any, HAB scientists who have made breakthrough contributions in so many areas. But Dr. Chinain has made significant contributions in taxonomy, toxicology, ecology, biogeography and public health of HABs during

her career. She has been a mentor and inspiration to many of us. Her leadership and persistence to produce repeated breakthroughs in helping mitigate a much-neglected tropical disease as evidenced by her contribution to the Experts Report on Ciguatera (2020), the Global HAB Status Report (2021) and Chapter 3 on Benthic HABs in the Joint FAO-IOC-IAEA Technical Guidance for the Implementation of Early Warning Systems for Harmful Algal Blooms (2023).

ISSHA 2023 Patrick Gentien Young Scientist Award

Tomohiro Nishimura received the ISSHA 2023 Patrick Gentien Award for his outstanding contribution to our understanding of the physiology, ecology and toxicity of harmful algae. He has proven to be a productive, collaborative, and

Tomohiro Nishimura, ISSHA Patrick Gentien Award 2023

impactful young scientist. His nomination was presented by Prof. Masao Adachi: Tomohiro Nishimura's research has focused on toxic dinoflagellates and diatoms in Japan and Oceania, with particular emphasis on benthic harmful algal bloom (BHAB) genera, including the macroalgae-associated *Alexandrium* (his original discovery), *Gambierdiscus*, and *Prorocentrum*, and harmful algal bloom (HAB) diatom genus *Pseudo-nitzschia*. His work included extensive studies of cell density and dynamics, the establishment of over 2,000 isolates, morphological and molecular phylogenetic classifications, toxicity and toxin production assessments, growth experiments under different environmental conditions, and the development of a sensitive and species-specific molecular biological detection and quantification method (qPCR assay). His research has elucidated species diversity, relations between species/clades and toxicity/toxin production, and the physiology and ecology of BHAB dinoflagellates and HAB diatoms.

His pioneering studies have significantly advanced the field of BHAB dinoflagellates and *Pseudo-nitzschia* research, and provided essential information for risk assessment of these organisms. His discovery of a *Prorocentrum* strain with high productivity of dinophysistoxin-1 has contributed to the industrial production of this compound as a standard material in Japan. In addition, his work on *Pseudo-nitzschia* has contributed to refining risk profiles and improving cell density trigger levels in the New Zealand Marine Phytoplankton Monitoring Programme, reducing unnecessary testing and bivalve harvest closures in New Zealand in the future. He has also contributed to research on other HAB/BHAB genera, such as *Azadinium*, *Coolia*, *Fukuyoa*, *Heterocapsa*, *Ostreopsis*, and toxic cyanobacteria genera with collaborators from various countries.

Maureen Keller Awards to best student presentations

Serena Sung-Clarke (best oral presentation). Serena is a Ph.D. candidate with the Massachusetts Institute of Technology/Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (MIT/WHOI) Joint Program in Applied Ocean Sciences. She is advised by WHOI's Dr. Michael Brosnahan. She

Serena Sung-Clarke

Kristof Möller

Loïc Plessis

Lucia Beatrice Cal

studies the ecology of the dinoflagellate *Dinophysis* using a mix of field observations, culture experiments, and molecular methods. Her presentation at ICHA2023 described her work investigating subsurface accumulation and phased sexual reproduction in a *Dinophysis* bloom population in the absence of their obligate prey. Serena earned her Bachelor of Arts with high honors from Swarthmore College in 2019, with majors in Biology and Political Science. As an undergraduate, she worked in Dr. Elizabeth Vallen's lab, studying cnidarian immune protein interactions. Her interest in HABs started during the summer of 2018, when she had the opportunity to work with Dr. Jacques Oliver and Dr. Lester Yuan at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) analyzing freshwater and estuarine nutrient impairment and HAB occurrence. Before starting her Ph.D., Serena spent two years working for Cadmus on USEPA contracts, developing watershed health assessments, leading regulatory workshops for water utilities, and com-

piling research on chemical contamination. Now, as a student in the Brosnahan Lab, she pries into the mysterious lives of *Dinophysis* dinoflagellates and hopes to shed light on their response to starvation and life history processes.

Kristof Möller (*oral presentation honorable mention*). Kristof Möller, from the Alfred-Wegener-Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (Bremerhaven, Germany), received the Maureen Keller Award for his presentation about: "Ichthyotoxicity of the harmful dinoflagellate *Alexandrium pseudogonyaulax* and predator-prey interactions with the copepod *Acartia tonsa*" co-authored by Urban Tillmann, Magdalena Pöchhacker, Bernd Krock, Elisabeth Varga, Florian Koch, Thomas Harris and Cédric L. Meunier.

Kristof Möller is a Ph.D. student in the Ecological Chemistry section at the Alfred-Wegener-Institute. His doctoral thesis focuses on the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium pseudogonyaulax* in Northern European waters, particularly

considering its recent increase in abundance. His research involves investigating bottom-up and top-down population controls of *A. pseudogonyaulax*, as well as assessing its toxicological effects on other trophic levels including zooplankton and fish. Additionally, he analyses how *A. pseudogonyaulax* has been introduced and what factors have contributed to its proliferation by conducting a time series analysis of long-term monitoring programs in Sweden, Norway, Denmark, and Germany. Kristof earned his Master of Science degree in biochemistry and Bachelor of Science degree in chemistry and biochemistry from the Ludwig-Maximilians-University in Munich. His master's thesis, which focused on establishing a method for extracting and quantifying vitamin B₁₂ from seawater, sparked his interest in marine sciences. His research interests now encompass biotoxins, harmful algae blooms, and marine carbon dioxide removal techniques.

Loïc Plessis (*best poster presentation*). Loïc Plessis, PhD student from the French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea (Ifremer) and Nantes University, was awarded the Maureen Keller Student Award for the best poster presentation titled "Portimine from *Vulcanodinium rugosum* induces severe pyroptosis in primary skin cells through ribotoxic stress response (RSR)" co-authored by Léana Gorse, Korian Lhaute, Fabienne Hervé, Damien Réveillon, Stéphanie Brédif, Patrice Brehmer, Étienne Meunier, and Philipp Hess.

Loïc's scientific journey began with a two-year diploma in applied chemistry at the Institute of Technology of Orléans University, followed by an internship in organic chemistry synthesis at Rothamsted Research, United Kingdom. He then pursued a double course in chemistry and biotechnology at two engineering schools at Strasbourg University, in European School of Chemistry, Polymers and Materials Science (ECPM) and European School of Biotechnology (ESBS). To complete his engineering diploma, he interned at the phycotoxin laboratory of Ifremer Nantes, working for the first time on toxic microalgae. Specifically, Loïc studied the chemical diversity of two toxic microalgae belonging to the genus *Azadinium*.

Currently, Loïc is conducting his

PhD research under the supervision of Dr. Philipp Hess between two laboratories: the METALG laboratory at Ifremer Nantes, Phytox unit, and the Groupe Rocher skin lab in Paris. His research focuses on investigating the impact of various microalgae and their metabolites on skin cells, with an emphasis on inflammatory effects. This includes studying both toxic microalgae for Ifremer, such as *Ostreopsis* and *Vulcanodinium*, and microalgae of cosmetic interest for Groupe Rocher. During his PhD, Loïc had the opportunity to collaborate with the Institute of Pharmacology and Structural Biology (IPBS) of Toulouse, which helped clarifying the mechanism of action of the emerging toxin Por-timine from *V. rugosum*.

Lucia Beatrice Cal (*poster presentation honorable mention*). Lucia Beatrice Cal received the Maureen Keller Student Award for her poster entitled: “Morphological and phylogenetic characterization of toxic *Coolia malayensis* from the West Philippine Sea”, co-authored by Robert Jay Ramos, Juri Nazareth Ochotorena, Gian Carlo Gaetos, and Dr. Deo Florence Onda.

Lucia is a MS Marine Science student affiliated with the Microbial Oceanography Laboratory of the Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines. She earned her Bachelor of Science degree, majoring in Biology, from the same university and took an interest in microalgae while taking a phycology elective as an undergrad.

She works as a research associate while pursuing her Master’s degree under the “Real-time Monitoring and Early Warning for HABs Using High Throughput Imaging and Molecular Methods (the HABs Watch Project)” led by her adviser Dr. Onda, which aims to use a combination of machine-learning and the Imaging Flow Cytobot/IFCB (McLane Laboratories) to develop a real-time detection system for harmful phytoplankton. She is tasked with establishing and maintaining diatom and dinoflagellate monocultures, but is also being trained in using the IFCB. Her research is currently focused on benthic dinoflagellates, whose distribution patterns are not well-studied in the Philippines, and marine microbial ecology.

Top left, Local Organizers recognition at the closing ceremony (photo LOC ICHA 2023); Bottom left, Hiroshima Gokoku Shrine, location of cocktails before Gala dinner (photo E Bresnan); ISSHA most senior Council members relax at the Kagura performance: top right, Ichiro Imai-san and Ian Jenkinson (photo I. Jenkinson) and bottom right, ISSHA (past) President, Wayne Litaker (Photo E Bresnan).

First report of a *Pyrodinium bahamense* bloom off Djibouti, western Gulf of Aden

Fig. 1. A. Map of the study area and location of the dinoflagellate bloom off Djibouti, western Gulf of Aden. B. Satellite image from Sentinel-2 on September 22, 2023 showing high chlorophyll concentrations in coastal waters of Tadjoura, Djibouti. (C) Red water discoloration related to the bloom. (D). Fish mortality on the beach of the Moucha/Maskali Islands.

During summer, southwest Monsoon winds in the Gulf of Aden (GoA) induce an eastward outflow of surface waters. This outflow is compensated by an upwelling of cold, nutrient-rich deep water at the extreme west, in the Gulf of Tadjoura and the southern part of the Strait of Bab-el-Mandeb strait [1]. To the west of the GoA, these nutrient-rich waters are characterized by high chlorophyll concentrations [2]. In late summer, September 2023, a water discoloration event (red tide) accompanied by significant fish mortalities was observed in the Gulf of Tadjoura (Fig. 1). To understand the origin of this phenomenon, phytoplankton samples were collected using a 20- μm mesh size plankton net (Hydro-Bios) and environmental conditions were assessed at the sampling site off the Moucha/Maskali Islands on September 21, 2023 using a multiparameter probe (CastAway-CTD). Cells were identified by light microscopy [3] and enumerated using an Olym-

pus inverted microscope (IX70-S8F2, Japan) [3]. The plankton samples revealed that the seawater discoloration was caused by a potentially toxic dinoflagellate, *Pyrodinium bahamense* [4]. The bloom, located near the coast, between the Marine Protected Areas of the Moucha/Maskali Islands and the city of Tadjourah, was dense enough to be detected by satellite imagery (Fig. 1. A). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that an analysis has been conducted in the Gulf of Tadjoura during a phytoplankton bloom. *Pyrodinium bahamense* developed a nearly monospecific bloom, reaching a density of 5.3×10^6 cells. L^{-1} . Other potentially toxic dinoflagellates such as *Dinophysis miles*, *Dinophysis caudata*, and *Lingulodinium polyedra* were detected but at very low cellular densities. Environmental parameters measured during the event were: salinity 36.6; temperature 32.9°C; pH 8.67, conductivity 64009 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and seawater density 1021.9 kg/m^3 .

Previous observations of *P. bahamense* blooms in Yemeni and Saudi Arabian coastal waters suggest that such blooms typically occur in late summer, although previous studies recorded lower cell densities of 10^4 – 10^5 cells. L^{-1} [5,6]. Our observations align with these findings, indicating that this species is present in coastal waters of the Red Sea in significant quantities in late summer through early autumn (June to October) [5,6]. In addition, toxicological analyses conducted on cultures of this species as well as water samples from the southern Red Sea region confirmed the toxicity of this species [6], which could explain the fish mortalities. Studies are needed to confirm the toxicity of the GoA strains of *P. bahamense* and their ability to produce toxins similar to those of the Red Sea strains. This is crucial for enhancing our understanding of associated risks and implementing preventive measures when necessary.

Acknowledgements

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References

1. Yao F & I Hoteit 2015. *PloS ONE* 10:e0119951
2. Gittings JA et al 2017. *Remote Sens Environ* 189:56–66
3. Mertens KN et al 2015. *Harmful Algae* 41:1–24
4. Likumahua S et al 2022. *Mar Pollut Bull*:185, 114340
5. Alkawri A et al 2016. *Turkish J Fish Aquat Sci* 16:275–282
6. Banguera-Hinestroza E et al 2016. *Harmful Algae* 55:163–171

Authors

Mahamoud A Chirdon & Moussa Mahdi Ahmed, Observatoire Regional de Recherche sur l'Environnement et le Climat ORREC-CERD, Route de l'aéroport, B.P. 486, Djibouti – ville, Djibouti

Kenneth N Mertens & Nicolas Chomérat, Ifremer, LITTORAL, Place de la Croix, 29900 Concarneau, France

Philipp Hess, Ifremer, PHYTOX, Nantes, F-44311, France

Email corresponding author: moudass2023@gmail.com

Fig. 2. A. Light micrographs of *Pyrodinium bahamense* cells from a sample collected on September 20, 2023, off the coast of Moucha/Maskali Islands. B. Epifluorescence micrograph showing epithelial plates and the Apical Pore Complex (APC) (scale bar = 10 μm).

Green tides of *Eutreptiella marina* (Euglenophyta) in Yelapa, Bahía de Banderas Jalisco-Nayarit México

Fig. 1. Map of Yelapa area, municipality of Cabo Corrientes, in Banderas Bay Jalisco-Nayarit México.

In May 2022 a massive algal bloom caused greenish discolorations along the beaches of Yelapa Jalisco México (Fig. 1) (-105° 44'N; 20°48'W). Microscopical observations of bloom samples showed that the dominant microalgae agreed with the description of *Eutreptiella marina* by Norris [1] (Fig. 2). Single cells were about 15-80 μm long and 3-15 μm wide with a variable shape ranging from spherical to very elongated. A vertical profile of physical properties measured at the time of the bloom showed marked gradients of temperature, with 25.71°C at the surface, ~ 20°C at 10m and 14.56°C at the bottom, and a slight salinity gradient (34.08-34.24) (Fig. 3). Chlorophyll *a* reached values of 32.28 and 16.73 mg m^{-3} at the surface and 70 m respectively. It is well known that the genus *Eutreptiella* includes several species whose toxicity has been related to the cellular content of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Other *Eutreptiella* spp are used as pollution indicators [2, 3, 4]. These high biomass blooms (up to 7 million cells.l⁻¹) (Fig. 2) represent a latent risk for fish and other organisms in the bay. Likewise, its notable abundance can create severe anoxia causing mortality of marine fauna [5]. The bloom described here was one of the most extensive HAB of a eugleno-

phyte microalgae ever reported in this area. The causes of this exceptional *E. marina* event are not very clear yet. It is well known that the occurrence of this species in Yelapa is favored by water circulation during the cold season. Upwelling of cold and nutrient-rich waters on the coast creates optimal conditions for proliferation of micro-

algae [3, 6]. An alternative explanation is that during that HAB event, Yelapa coasts were under the influence of El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) in its cold La Niña phase (2021-2022). This atmospheric mode probably affected the oceanographic conditions that promoted the bloom of *E. marina*. Runoff of terrigenous material in rivers and local wastewater discharges may have contributed to promote these HAB events [7]. *Eutreptiella marina* is said to prefer waters with high concentrations of organic matter, ferrous compounds, and ammonium salts [1, 8]. Complementary studies should focus on the impacts of ROS produced by *E. marina* on the marine fauna, because these compounds cause erratic behavior and considerable mucus secretion by fish gills (e.g., *Xenotilus californiensis*) in Bahía de Banderas [5]. During the bloom, no negative impacts were detected on the local marine fauna. There was no health impact from recreational activities either. Nevertheless, it is important to continue monitoring this area to identify spatial and temporal trends in *E. marina* populations and their impact.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Project "Implementation of a Marine Environmental Monitoring Programme for Islas Marietas and Isla Isabel National Parks,

Fig. 2. Yelapa green tide of *Eutreptiella marina* during May 14-26, 2022. Micrograph of single cells showing different shapes (2A-E) taken under an inverted microscope with phase contrast. Aggregates at 200x (2F) and live cells filaments (2H) during the event. Photograph 2G courtesy of Océano. Rafael García de Quevedo.

Nayarit, México". Our thanks to Ocean. Rafael García de Quevedo for providing photos of the discolorations

References

1. Norris RE 1964. *New Zealand J Bot* 2: 258-278
2. Kim CS et al 1999. *J Plankton Res* 21:2105-2115
3. Hernández-Becerril DU 2014. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad Sup* 85:44-53
4. Cho K et al 2022. *Antioxidants* 11:206
5. Cortés-Lara MC et al 2010. *HAN* 42:12-13
6. Olli K et al 1996. *J Plankton Res* 18: 1587-1604
7. Pérez de Silva CV et al 2003. *Ciencias Marinas* 49:1-16
8. Sansón M et al 2005. *VIERAEA* 33:29-40

Fig. 3. Vertical distribution of temperature, salinity and depth in Yelapa, Jalisco during HAB events of *Eutreptiella marina* on May 26, 2022. Data obtained with a Sontek CastAway® CTD from Xylem and graphed with Ocean Data View software.

Authors

María del Carmen Cortés-Lara, Ana Mercedes Cupul-Velázquez & Amílcar Levi Cupul-Magaña, LEMAC- CUCOSTA-Universidad de Guadalajara, México

Mariana Cupul-Cortés, IIO-Universidad Autónoma de Baja California, México.

E-mail corresponding author: delcarmen.cortes@academicos.udg.mx

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Cook Islands benthic and epiphytic dinoflagellates

Fig. 1. (Left) Photograph of Rarotonga, Cook Islands from the air and (right) map of sites sampled in the Cook Islands, November 2022

In 1979, the genus *Gambierdiscus* Adachi & Fukuyo was described, with the type species being *G. toxicus* [1]. In 2017, in an article in HANews [2], it was noted that ‘fourteen species of *Gambierdiscus* had been described with three of these being described in 2016, an increase of nearly 30% in one year’. Since then, the number has increased to nineteen species being recorded in AlgaeBase to date [1]. Seventeen of those species have been recorded in the Pacific region. The Cook Islands has been of interest because of the high rates of ciguatera poisoning in past years, due to the presence of *Gambierdiscus polynesiensis*, a ciguatoxin (CTX) producer [3]. A concern is that, with warmer seas being recorded in coastal waters of Aotearoa New Zealand, species found in the Cook Islands and other Pacific Islands may establish or, if already present, proliferate in the subtropical northern waters. It is therefore critical for risk assessments to be carried out to know what toxin producing genera are likely to be of future concern.

In November 2022, a research trip was carried out in Rarotonga, Cook Islands (Fig. 1) and samples were collected (Fig. 2) for metabarcoding (in preparation) and for isolations of living cells. The dominant *Gambi-*

erdiscus species, as determined by DNA sequencing of cultured isolates, was *G. australes*. This species was isolated from macroalgal samples (*Turbinaria* sp. and *Halimeda* sp.) collected from the sites Papua and Titikaveka, and isolates tested were all maitotoxin (MTX-1) producers (Table 1). No CTX was detected. One of the many strains of *G. australes* isolated is now maintained in the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae (CICCM) as CAWD445.

At Muri Lagoon (Fig. 1), *G. honu* was successfully isolated from samples collected from *Padina* sp. and another isolate (CAWD446) was isolated from *Turbinaria* sp. at the Papua site. *G. honu* is a known producer of MTX-7 and gambierone analogues [4], but interestingly isolate CAWD446 did not produce MTX-7 above the limit of detection for this method (Table 1).

Gambierdiscus pacificus (CAWD449) was also isolated from *Padina* sp. in

Fig. 2. (Top left) Sampling in deeper water, Rarotonga, Cook Islands, November 2022; (top right) sampling at Tikioki with Ministry of Marine Resources staff; (lower left) passive sampling devices; (lower right) typical shallow coastal lagoon site.

Table 1. Biotoxins produced by *Gambierdiscus* species isolated from the Cook Islands, 2022.

Species	CICCM code	Toxins pg/cell							
		G	44-MG	MTX-1	MTX-5	MTX-6	MTX-7	P-CTX-3B, 3C, 4A, 4B	Iso-CTX-3B /C, 4A/B
<i>G. australes</i>	CAWD445	<0.01	311	14	0.8	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
<i>G. honu</i>	Muri16*	4.4	159	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	11.2	<0.01	<0.01
<i>G. honu</i>	CAWD446	42.5	138	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
<i>G. lapillus</i>	CAWD451	0.6	108	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
<i>G. pacificus</i>	CAWD449	5.7	210	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

*Not in Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae (CICCM); G; gambierone; 44-MG: 44-methylgambierone; MTX: maitotoxin; P-CTX: Pacific ciguatoxin.

Muri Lagoon and produced 44 methylgambierone and gambierone, but no CTXs (Table 1).

An extremely slow growing *Gambierdiscus* isolate (yet to be tested for toxin production) was isolated from a sample collected at the island of Aitutaki, north of Rarotonga. This proved to be *G. lapillus* (CAWD451) as determined by DNA sequencing. It was isolated from the macroalga *Turbinaria ornata*. No CTXs were detected (Table 1). *Gambierdiscus* cells were also isolated from *Padina* sp. but these did not survive in culture.

Gambierdiscus species not observed in live samples during the current study, but which have been reported in the Cook Islands previously, include *G. lapillus* [5], *G. cheloniae* (a producer of MTX-6) [6] and *G. polynesiensis* (CTX producer) [7]. It was noted by Smith et al. [8], during a 2014 field trip, that although *Gambierdiscus* was present in high numbers at most sites (with five species being isolated and species determined by DNA sequencing and eight *Gambierdiscus* species being recorded using metabarcoding).

At Tikioki (Fig. 1) in November 2022, *Alexandrium* sp. 2 [9] was isolated from an artificial substrate which had been deployed for 48 hours. Cells were also isolated from samples deployed at Betela but did not survive. The cells were identified by DNA sequencing, as they were only present in their non-motile stage and were difficult to identify by microscopic observation (CAWD450).

Despite being in culture for 10 months no motile cells have been observed to date. The isolate was tested for paralytic shellfish toxins by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry but none were detected.

Ostreopsis lenticularis (CAWD447) and *Coolia malyensis* were isolated from samples collected from a submerged palm frond at the outer reef and were also identified by DNA sequencing. Production of palytoxin-like compounds by *Ostreopsis lenticularis* was assessed using a recently developed method that monitors the intact analogues (unpublished) and the oxidative cleavage method [10], but none was detected. Not isolated, but observed in most samples, were the dinoflagellate genera *Ampidinium* and *Prorocentrum*.

There did not appear to be a preferred habitat for *Gambierdiscus* or *Ostreopsis*, with species isolated from a wide range of macroalgal genera, including *Halimeda*, *Padina* and *Turbinaria*. The artificial substrate, *Asparagopsis*, and even a floating palm frond also gave rise to successful unialgal cultures. Species recorded by establishment of cell cultures from the Cook Islands so far include *G. australes*, *G. caribaeus*, *G. cheloniae*, *G. honu*, *G. lapillus*, *G. pacificus*, and *G. polynesiensis*. This supports the hypothesis that toxic species of *Gambierdiscus* could establish on the macroalgae occurring in northern Aotearoa New Zealand, with habitat unlikely to be a barrier. It is not yet known whether the diversity of *Gambierdiscus*

species is particularly high for the Cook Islands, or whether the species remain underestimated globally. As *Gambierdiscus* has been recorded on one occasion, and the related genus *Fukuyoa* on many occasions, in Aotearoa New Zealand it is only a matter of time before favourable conditions result in a proliferation of these dinoflagellates resulting in blooms.

References

1. Guiry in Guiry & Guiry 2021. *AlgaeBase*. <https://www.algaebase.org/>; searched 20 July 2023
2. Rhodes L et al. 2017. *Harmful Algae News* 56: 1-4
3. Rongo T & van Woesik 2013. *Toxicon* 64: 87-95
4. Murray JS et al. 2022. *Mar Drugs* 20: 453
5. Rhodes L et al. 2020. *Harmful Algae News (IOC newsletter)*. 65: 10-11
6. Smith KF et al. 2016. *Harmful Algae* 60: 45-56
7. Rhodes L et al. 2014. *Harmful Algae* 39: 185-190
8. Smith et al. 2023 (in prep)
9. Nishimura T et al. 2021. *Harmful Algae* 104: 101924
10. Selwood AI et al 2012. *Toxicon* 60: 810-820

Authors

Lesley Rhodes, Kirsty Smith, Sam Murray, Emillie Passfield, Lucy Thompson & Jacob Thomson-Laing, Cawthron Institute, Private Bag 2, Nelson, New Zealand

Charlee McLean & Phoebe Argyle, Ministry of Marine Resources, Cook Islands

Email corresponding author:
Lesley.rhodes@cawthron.org.nz

The Next International Conference on Harmful Algae (21st ICHA) is coming

Time flies, and it feels like just yesterday that the 20th edition of the International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) unfolded. Held biennially, the most recent gathering took place from November 5 to 10, 2023, at the Grand Prince Hotel in Hiroshima, Japan. Now, preparations are underway for the upcoming conference, slated to take place in Chile, specifically in Punta Arenas on the northern coast of the Strait of Magellan at the southern tip of South America. The 21st edition of ICHA is scheduled from October 19 to 24, 2025, at the Dreams Hotel in Punta Arenas (Fig. 1).

These conferences are made possible through the tireless work, dedication, and collaboration of the International Scientific Society of Harmful Algae (ISSHA). Their support and guidance are instrumental in their success. The decision to host the 21st ICHA in Chile stems from a request made during the development of the 19th edition of the conference, held in La Paz, Mexico, in 2021. The request was presented to the Assembly of ISSHA, then chaired by Dr. Vera Trainer from the USA. Currently, Dr. Dedmer van de Waal from the Netherlands holds this position, who receives the post chaired by Dr. Wayne Litaker from the USA (2021-2023).

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) represent a pressing global issue marked by a rise in frequency, scope, and impact. The increase in these events is attributed to several factors, including extreme

oceanographic climate fluctuations, such as El Niño and La Niña, the Antarctic Oscillation, and the broader effects of climate change. Additionally, nutrient overabundance from domestic and industrial effluent discharge into water bodies contributes to HAB proliferation. Furthermore, certain microalgae morphologies pose a threat to fish gills, particularly in the aquaculture industry. HABs, stemming from diverse microalgae species, can produce potent phyco-toxins that accumulate in shellfish and pose a great threat to public health and aquatic ecosystems, including aquaculture systems (Fig. 2). Their severe impacts extend to social and economic sectors, exerting a significant toll on affected communities. In the last decades, HAB events have been escalating in frequency and expanding geographically, exacerbated by extreme oceanographic climatic events and global climate change. These blooms also affect freshwater ecosystems like lakes and rivers, prompting scientists worldwide to intensify efforts to understand their dynamics and impacts. Each country or region has created capabilities and inverted resources for monitoring and managing HAB occurrences. Effective policy decisions and management strategies are imperative in averting and mitigating the adverse effects of these events.

With eighteen months remaining until the next conference, now is an opportune moment to underscore the significance of such scientific gatherings and the responsibility they entail for Chile as hosts. It's crucial to motivate attendance at the upcoming conference to be held in Chile. Emphasizing the importance of convening in the Southern Hemisphere, specifically at the southernmost tip of the Americas, in Chile, will be paramount. Additionally, the importance of Southern Chile as a natural laboratory and a global "hot spot" of HAB events, as well as the historical, geographical, and diverse natural attractions of Chile's southernmost region—the Magellan region—as the gateway to the Antarctic continent, will serve to entice participation further (Fig. 3).

These conferences typically convene between 400 and 600 attendees from no fewer than 50 countries, presenting a significant undertaking for the host country, organizing institution, and local organizing committee. Since December 2023, the Local Organizing Committee has convened several meetings, establishing various subcommittees tasked with orchestrating the logistics and commitments associated with this scientific gathering. A substantial contingent from the national and Latin American scientific communities is expected, and the conference will prominently address HABs and marine phyco-toxins. Nevertheless, the participation and support of the entire global community, spanning diverse institutions and individuals engaged with HABs, are encouraged to contribute to the planning and execution of this crucial scientific event through the International Scientific Committee.

The upcoming 21st edition of ICHA, scheduled to take place in Punta Arenas, Chile, marks the third occasion the conference will be hosted in a Latin American country. Previous editions were held in Brazil (Florianópolis) in 2016 and Mexico (La Paz) in 2021. Notably, three-quarters of these conferences have historically been hosted in countries located in the northern hemisphere. The exceptions to this trend include meetings held in South Africa, Australia, New Zealand, and Brazil.

Authors

Leonardo Guzmán, Chair 21st ICHA Local Organizing Committee, Instituto de Fomento Pesquero, Puerto Montt

Máximo Frangópulos, 1st Vice-Chair Universidad de Magallanes, Punta Arenas

Patricio Díaz, 2nd Vice-Chair, Universidad de Los Lagos, Puerto Montt

Email contact: leonardo.guzman@ifop.cl

Fig. 1. Dreams Hotel in Punta Arenas, conference venue for the 21st ICHA conference venue in Punta Arenas, Magallanes, Chile.

Fig. 2. "Marea café" (brown tide) of *Heterosigma akashiwo* in Comau Fjord, Los Lagos. Photo by Pamela Urrutia

Fig. 3. Towers of Paine National Park, Chilean Patagonia. Photo University of Magallanes

Photo B Ben-Gigirey

Eds-in-chief

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Compiled and edited by

Beatriz Reguera, Centro Oceanográfico de Vigo,
IEO (CSIC)

Subida a Radio Faro 50, 36390 Vigo, Spain

Tel: +34 986 492111

Fax: +34 986 498626

Email: beatriz.reguera@ieo.csic.es

and

Eileen Bresnan, Marine Scotland, Victoria Road,
Aberdeen AB11DB, Scotland

Tel.: +44 122 4876544

Fax: +44 1224295511

Email: eileen.bresnan@gov.scot

FAO Esther Garrido

IAEA Carlos M Alonso

Project Coordinator

Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC Science and Communication
Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen,
Universitetsparken 4, 2100 Copenhagen 0, Denmark

Tel.: +45 23 26 02 46

E-mail: h.enevoldsen@unesco.org

Lay-out

Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen,
Denmark

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